

Dyes derived from Phenanthraquinone.

Part V.

Phenanthraphenazinazines.

BY

ANUKUL CHANDRA SIRCAR

AND

PARESH CHANDRA DUTT.

In continuation of the work of Sircar and Dutt (J. C. S. T., 1922, 121, 1944), Sircar and Sircar (J. C. S. T., 1923, 123, 1559) and Sircar and Roy (J. C. S. T., 1924, 125, 543), this investigation was undertaken with the object of finding out if the colours of the phenanthraphenazines (Watson and Dutt, J. C. S. T., 1921, 119, 1211) could be deepened specially towards blue and green, by the introduction of an additional chromophoric azine ring in their molecules. Some phenanthraphenazinazines have now been prepared by condensing 2:3-diamido-phenazine (Ullmann and Manthner. B., 35, 4302) with phenanthraquinone and its derivatives.

These compounds all contain two azine rings in their molecules and are very suitable for comparing with the

* The first four papers of this series have appeared in the Journal of the Chemical Society of London (T. 1922, p. 1944 *et seq.*; T. 1923, p. 1559; T. 1924, p. 543).

corresponding compounds containing only one azine ring (Watson and Dutt, *oc. cit.*; Sircar and Dutt, *loc. cit.*).

A comparison, made below, of the colours of the dyeings on wool of a number of phenanthraphenazinazines described in this paper with those of the corresponding phenanthraphenazines (Watson and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) and phenanthranaphthazines (Sircar and Dutt, *loc. cit.*), will show that the colours of the phenanthraphenazines can be easily deepened and fuller and brighter shades obtained by the introduction of an additional heterocyclic azine ring in their molecules.

	Name of the compound.	Colour of the dyeing on wool.
1.	2-amino-phenanthraphenazinazine ...	Very deep brown.
	2-amino-phenanthraphenazine ...	Yellow.
2.	2:7-dinitrophenanthraphenazinazine ...	Deep maroon.
	2:7-dinitrophenanthranaphthazine ...	Light yellow.
3.	2-hydroxy-phenanthraphenazinazine ...	Violet-brown.
	2-hydroxy-phenanthranaphthazine ...	Yellow.
4.	2:7-dibromo-phenanthraphenazinazine ...	Reddish-brown.
	2:7-dibromo-phenanthranaphthazine ...	Light yellow.

Though the phenanthraphenazinazines excel the corresponding mono-azines in so far as they dye deeper and fuller shades, the deepening of the colour is in every case towards brownish shades and none of the compounds dye in blue or green colour.

The azinazines, described in this paper, are remarkably stable substances and insoluble in the ordinary solvents. They are however soluble in pyridine. They dissolve in strong sulphuric acid with characteristic colour; water precipitates them unchanged as light, flocculent masses, well adapted for dyeing on wool (from an acid bath).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenanthraphenazinazine.

The precipitate produced by boiling 1.04 grams of phenanthraquinone and 1.05 grams of 2:3-diamido-phenazine

in 60 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, separated from hot pyridine, on the addition of hot water, in chocolate-coloured microscopic needles not melting below 290°. The substance dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a violet colour and dyes wool in reddish-brown shades. (Found : N=14·88, $C_{22}H_{14}N_4$ requires N=14·66 per cent.)

For the preparation of the compounds described below, separate solutions of equimolecular quantities of the quinone and the 2:3-diamidophenazine, in glacial acetic acid, were boiled together for some time; the amorphous brownish precipitates obtained were, except where otherwise stated, purified by precipitation from hot pyridine solution by the addition of hot water. They invariably separated in an amorphous condition and could not be obtained crystalline. None of the compounds melts below 290°.

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from 2:7-dinitrophenanthraquinone (boiling for one hour), was purified by extracting for some time with a little acetic acid and precipitating the residue from pyridine. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a violet colour and dyes wool in greenish-brown shades. (Found : N=17·95. $C_{22}H_{12}O_4N_6$ requires N=17·80 per cent.)

The three following compounds were purified in a similar way to the preceding one.

4:5-Dinitrophenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from 4:5-dinitrophenanthraquinone, was obtained as a chocolate-black powder dissolving in sulphuric acid with a blue colour and dyeing chocolate shades on wool. (Found : N=18·05 per cent.)

2-Nitro-phenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from 2-nitro-phenanthraquinone (boiling for 45 minutes), dissolves in sulphuric acid with a bluish-violet colour and dyes wool in chocolate-brown shades. The substance is

soluble in nitro-benzene or aniline (Found: $N=16.6$. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires $N=16.39$ per cent.)

4-Nitro-phenanthraphenazinazine,—resembles the 2-nitro compound in all its properties. (Found: $N=16.86$ per cent.).

2-Bromo-phenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from 2-bromo-phenanthraquinone (boiling for half an hour), was purified by extracting for some time with acetic acid and precipitating the residue from pyridine. It was obtained as a chocolate-brown precipitate. It gave a blue colouration with sulphuric acid and dyed wool in reddish-brown shades. (Found: $N=12.31$, $C_{20}H_{13}N_4Br$ requires $N=12.15$ per cent.).

2:7-Dibromophenanthraphenazinazine,—was obtained, in the usual way as a chocolate precipitate, from 2:7-dibromophenanthraquinone (boiling for two hours). It gave with sulphuric acid a violet colouration and dyed wool in deep reddish-brown shades. (Found: $N=11.0$. $C_{20}H_{12}N_4Br_2$ requires $N=10.37$ per cent.)

Dibromophenanthraphenazinazine,—was prepared from dibromophenanthraquinone of D. R. P. 222206 (boiling for 45 minutes). It gave a blue colouration with sulphuric acid and dyed wool in reddish-brown shades. (Found; $N=11.01$ per cent.).

Dibromonitrophenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from dibromonitrophenanthraquinone (Mukherjee and Watson, J. C. S. T., 1916, 109, 622) and obtained as a chocolate precipitate (boiling for one hour), was purified by extracting with acetic acid. Its properties are like those of the preceding compound. (Found: $N=11.32$. $C H_{11}O_2N_5Br_2$ requires $N=11.96$ per cent.).

Bromodinitrophenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from bromodinitro-phenanthraquinone (Mukherjee and Watson, *loc. cit.*), was purified by extracting with acetic acid and then precipitated from pyridine solutions. The substance

dissolves in sulphuric acid with a bluish-violet colour and dyes wool in greenish-brown shades. (Found: $N=14.68$. $C_{22}H_{11}O_4N_6Br$ requires $N=15.24$ per cent.).

5-Bromo-4-nitro-phenanthraphenazinazine,— prepared from 5-bromo-4-nitrophenanthraquinone of m. p. $224-226^\circ$ (Mukherjee and Watson, *loc. cit.*), gave a violet colouration with sulphuric acid and dyed chocolate-brown shades on wool. (Found: $N=14.25$. $C_{22}H_{12}O_2N_6Br$ requires $N=13.83$ per cent.).

Bromo-2-nitrophenanthraphenazinazine,—was obtained as a chocolate precipitate (after two hours' boiling) from bromo-2-nitrophenanthraquinone (Mukherjee and Watson, *loc. cit.*), and purified by extracting with acetic acid. It dissolves in sulphuric acid with a blue colour and dyes wool in chocolate-brown shades. (Found: $N=14.09$ per cent.).

2-Aminophenanthraphenazinazine,—prepared from 2-amino-phenanthraquinone (boiling for 45 minutes), dissolves in sulphuric acid with a brownish black colour and dyes greenish-brown shades on wool. (Found: $N=16.75$. $C_{22}H_{15}N_6$ requires $N=17.63$ per cent.).

The hydroxy-derivatives described below were prepared by boiling molecular quantities of the quinone and the diamine in the minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid and purified by boiling with alcohol.

2:7-Dihydroxyphenanthraphenazinazine,— prepared from 2:7-dihydroxyphenanthraquinone, dissolved in sulphuric acid with a violet-black colour and dyed wool in violet-brown shades. (Found: $N=12.59$. $C_{22}H_{14}O_4N_4$ requires $N=13.52$ per cent.).

4:5-Dihydroxyphenanthraphenazinazine,—dyed chrome-mordanted and unmordanted wool in violet-brown shades. (Found: $N=12.82$ per cent.).

2-Hyd. oxyphenanthraphenazinazine,— was prepared from 2-hydroxyphenanthraquinone (boiling for two hours).

(Found: N=13·62. $C_{23}H_{14}ON_4$ requires N=14·07 per cent.).

4-hydroxyphenanthraphenazinazine,— prepared in a similar way to the preceding compound, was obtained as a black precipitate (Found: N=13·29 per cent.).

The properties of the mono-hydroxyphenanthraphenazinazines resemble those of the dihydroxy compounds.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY,
DACCA, BENGAL.

[*Received, Sept. 25, 24.*]
